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REPORT 11

STUDY 4:
PROTOTYPICALITY

| November 2024

The project Turning a Blind Eye to Scandal has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 892951

A version of this report has been published

Walter, A.S., Redlawsk, D.P. (2023). The Effects of Prototypicality on Punishment of in-Party Political Leaders' Immoral Behavior. In: Haller, A., Michael, H. (eds) Scandalogy 4. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-47156-8_10

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The Effect of Prototypicality on Punishment of Inparty Political Leaders' Immoral Behavior

Annemarie S. Walter & David P. Redlawsk

Introduction

Political scandals are part of everyday politics. Some political transgressors survive their publicized immoral behavior, while others have to leave their position. In recent years there has been increasing media focus on scandalous behavior at the highest levels of government, especially in the United States during the presidency of Donald Trump. Trump won election in 2016 despite consistent violations of what are normally widely held moral principles. For example, during his campaign he made fun of a disabled reporter, was heard on audio tape bragging that how he could treat women any way he wished because he was rich, and made payoffs to keep women accusing him of sexual assault quiet, just to name a few extreme examples. And yet, these moral violations clearly were not disqualifying in the eyes of enough American voters that he won not only the Republican nomination for President, but the general election as well.

As the Trump example, suggests, there is considerable heterogeneity in how and whether political candidates and officeholders are held accountable for their misconduct (e.g. Riera et al., 2013; Kauder & Potrafke, 2016) and that not all voters are equally likely to do so (Alexander, Bågenholm & Charron, 2020; Riera et al., 2013). This heterogeneity has puzzled scholars and stimulated extensive research to try to solve this question. Studies have shown that scandal and voter' characteristics, such as scandal type, the relevance of the scandal, gender and partisanship of the voter can help explain voters' heterogeneous responses to politicians' immoral behavior (Lee, 2015; Carlson, Ganiel & Hyde, 2000; Anduiza, Galego & Munoz, 2013). An important explanatory factor is shared partisanship, various studies report that voters are more lenient towards politicians involved in moral transgressions of a transgressor that is affiliated with their party, so-called in party politicians than politicians affiliated with another party, so-called outparty politicians (Bhatti, Hansen & Olsen, 2013; Anduiza, Galego & Munoz, 2013; Blais, Gidgengil, Kilibarda, 2017; Walter & Redlawsk, 2019; 2021; Costa et al. 2020; Solaz, De Vries & De Geus, 2019). Most of this latter work focuses on differences in moral judgments towards in and out-party candidates. Here, we focus only on in-party politicians in order to examine a key aspect of leadership, the extent to which an in-group leader is viewed as prototypical, and we do so in the context of moral transgressions. In so doing, we contribute to the handful of studies examining heterogeneity in voters' moral judgments of in-party politicians (Filindra & Harbridge-Yong, 2022).

Political scientists studying the heterogeneous voter responses to political scandals have paid little attention to the importance of group leader prototypicality. However, prototypicality in inter and intragroup processes has been extensively examined by social psychologists in primarily non-political contexts. Work on leader transgressions, which are defined as 'violations of social, moral or legal norms' (Abrams et al., 2013) and considered a subcategory of unethical leadership (Davies, Leicht & Abrams, 2022), finds that the prototypicality of group leaders is not to be neglected, including in the political realm (Chang, 2021). A few political scientists have examined politicians' prototypicality, but not in the context of moral transgressions (e.g. Severson, 2018). Others operationalize leader's prototypicality as to the nation, but not the leader's own party (Morais, Adams & Randsley de Moura, 2020).

Given the limited research and the need to better understand heterogeneous responses to moral violations by politicians, this study seeks to examine co-partisans responses to in-party politicians'

immoral behavior, by focusing on the importance of transgressing politicians' group prototypicality and the resulting evaluations by copartisans and their preferences for punishment of moral violations. We examine voters overall as well as specifically for the two U.S. partisan groups – Republicans and Democrats - separately.

This study focuses on politicians' moral transgressions, which are often precursors to political scandals, which are "actions or events involving certain kinds of transgressions which become known to others and are sufficiently serious to elicit a public response" (Thompson, 2000: 13). We look at whether voters' response to politicians' moral transgressions in terms of the politician's likeability and punitiveness are dependent on their group prototypicality. Punitiveness is people's intuitive desire for moral punishment and can be seen as a precursor to holding transgressive politicians accountable (Hoffman et al., 2018).

Using a sample of U.S. partisan voters, we conduct a between-subject survey embedded vignette experiment in which the transgressors' prototypicality was manipulated. We find considerable in-party heterogeneity in voter judgements. We do not, however, find an effect of prototypicality, but instead find that atypicality affects how partisans judge in-party leader involved in moral transgressions. When no information about prototypicality is provided voters assume the politician to be prototypical. Morally transgressive atypical in-party leaders are evaluated more negatively than morally transgressive prototypical party leaders and morally transgressive party leaders for whom typicality information is not provided. Partisans also prefer higher levels of punitiveness towards morally transgressive atypical in-party leaders. Democrats are somewhat less lenient than Republicans towards inparty transgressors, regardless of group prototypicality. Results suggest that being a prototypical group leader does not give Republican or Democratic politicians more transgression credit, but that atypicality reduces the likelihood that voters will accept moral violations by their own leaders.

This chapter is structured as follows: First, we will discuss the literature on group prototypicality and transgression credit and the literature on voters' responses to immoral behavior of politicians. Second, we will present our study design and stimulus material. Third, we report our analyses' results. Finally, we draw conclusions and reports avenues for further research.

Group Prototypicality and Transgression Credit

Group members differ in group prototypicality (Hogg, 2016), that is, how well a group member represents the group's standards, norms and values (Hogg, 2001). Prototypical group members represent what group members have in common and what distinguishes them from other groups (Van Knippenberg & Van Knippenberg, 2005). The notion of prototypicality is based on group similarity, intergroup differences, group memory, and group history (Van Knippenberg & Hogg, 2003). As the notion of prototypicality draws from intergroup comparisons, this means that group prototypicality is not fixed (Van Knippenberg & Van Knippenberg, 2005). Group members can manipulate their prototypicality by making outgroup comparisons and claiming that they represent group prototypicality (Reicher & Hopkins, 2003). Group leaders are assumed to be prototypical for the group. The more prototypical an individual group member is, the more likely that individual is to emerge as the group leader because members view this individual as best representing the identity of the group (Hogg, 2001; Hogg et al., 2012).

Group prototypicality matters for inter- and intragroup processes. Research shows that in and out-group transgressors are evaluated and treated differently (Abrams, Randsley de Moura & Travaglino, 2013). The field disagrees over which is judged more favorably and punished more leniently or

judged more unfavorably and punished more severely. Some studies show that ingroup members are more favorably judged than outgroup members when involved in transgressive behaviour (e.g. Randsley de Moura & Abrams, 2013; Abrams, Randsley de Moura & Travaglino, 2013). However, other research reports that ingroup transgressors are more derogated than outgroup transgressors (Randsley de Moura & Abrams, 2013), this is known as 'the black sheep effect'. The magnitude of the so-called black sheep effect is argued to differ for group members and depend on their status within the group, such as centrality to the group (Pinto et al., 2010), i.e. group leaders' transgressive behavior is evaluated differently than regular group member's behavior.

Ingroup transgressors threaten the norms within the group, the homogeneity of the group, and positive group image. Transgressions by group leaders are potentially an even larger group image threat as they also challenge the perception of the leader as prototype and question the loyalty of the member to the group, and the loyalty between group and leader (Adams et al., 2003). Research has shown that not all ingroup transgressors are equally benefiting from ingroup loyalty and bias (Randsley de Moura & Abrams, 2013). Group leaders committing a moral transgression are more favorably evaluated than other group members committing the same moral transgression (Randsley de Moura & Abrams, 2013); this includes political leaders (Randsley de Moura & Abrams, 2013). The notion that political leaders are held to a different standard than other party members is also found in a study on the use of political incivility (Frimer & Skitka, 2020). Most work focusing on how voters evaluate transgressions by politicians does not find a black sheep effect; instead voters are more lenient towards inparty politicians involved in moral transgressions compared to outparty politicians (Bhatti, Hansen & Olsen, 2013; Anduiza, Galego & Munoz, 2013; Blais, Gidgengil, Kilibarda, 2017; Walter & Redlawsk, 2019; 2021; Costa et al., 2020

The so-called transgression credit for leaders is dependent on several factors. First of all, leaders lose this so-called transgression credit when they lose their position, ex-leaders are not judged differently than other group members (Abrams et al., 2008). Second, the leader transgression credit seems absent when the transgression is self-serving and does not serve group interests (Abrams et al., 2013) or when the leader is not perceived as legitimate (Marques et al., 2021). Third, the effect tends to be mediated by the extent to which group members believe that the role of leader requires that the leader is supported (Abrams et al., 2018). Fourth, leader's transgression credit is not unrestricted. For instance, group members did not grant this transgression credit when the group leader's transgression was making racist connotations (Abrams et al., 2014). Fifth, leader's transgression credit is also dependent on group size. Members of proportionally larger groups are more tolerant towards their transgressive leaders than members of smaller-sized groups. Members of smaller-sized groups tend to evaluate the transgressive leader as they do other group members (Travaglino et al., 2016). Sixth, transgression credit is also dependent on whether the transgression is publicly known. Transgressions in private are less likely to be punished (Ashokkumar, Galaif & Swann Jr., 2019; Chang, 2021). Seventh, the willingness to accept transgressions by a leader depends on the strength of group identification. Deeply aligned members especially prioritize group reputation over moral concerns and are less likely to suggest punishment of transgressive leaders publicly (Ashokkumar, Galaif & Swann Jr., 2019). Eighth, not all ingroup transgressions are equally damaging to the group image. Finally, studies argue that leader transgression credit is dependent on their prototypicality, including for political leaders (Chang, 2021; Abrams et al., 2018).

Various studies show that transgressive prototypical leaders are evaluated more positively and punished more leniently than transgressive atypical leaders (Abrams et al., 2018). Other studies claim that prototypical leaders are more punished for their moral transgressions than atypical leaders as they constitute a larger threat to the group image than non prototypical leader

transgressors (Chang, 2021). Leaders' transgression credit dependent on group prototypicality would be moderated by members group identification. Some work suggesting that prototypical leaders would be in particular punished by strongly identifying group members (Chang, 2021).

On the basis of this literature we formulate the following hypotheses:

Prototypicality Hypothesis (H1): Voters evaluate a prototypical in-party politician committing a moral transgression more positively than an atypical inparty politician. Voters tend to express lower levels of punitiveness towards prototypical in-party politicians involved in moral transgressions than atypical inparty politicians.

Partisanship Strength Hypothesis (H2): Voters who strongly identify with the party will evaluate a prototypical in-party politician committing a moral transgression more positively than voters who weakly identify with the party. Voters who strongly identify with the party will have lower levels of punitiveness toward a prototypical inparty politician engaged in morally transgressive behavior than toward atypical inparty politicians.

Data and Methods

To test our hypotheses we designed a 2x3 between-subjects vignette experiment embedded in the 2022 Cooperative Election Study (CES) administered by YouGov. A sample of American voters was collected between 29 September 2022 and 8 November 2022 and consists of 815 respondents, 499 Democrats and 319 Republicans. Because we are interested in how co-partisans respond to their own leaders, voters who consider themselves independents not leaning to either party were not included in the sample.

Table 1 provides the basic descriptives for the sample. We use the unweighted CES sample for multivariate analysis. The unweighted sample is less female and more likely to be White, than American voters overall, and more likely to be Democrats. Because not all respondents provided complete data on key measures, our final sample for analysis is 786 respondents. See Table 1 for descriptives of the sample.

Table: Descriptives Sample

Characteristics	
Female	46.06%
White	80.99%
Democrats	60.43%
Republicans	39.57%
No high school education	4.83%
High school degree or some college	47.84
Batchelor's degree	34.10%
Postgraduate education	13.23%
Age	Mean=52.81 Standard Deviation=16.96

Note: N=786

Respondents first indicated their party preference, including whether they were strong, weak, or leaning party identifiers. They were then assigned to one of three versions of a moral violation vignette, with the political leader described as a co-partisan. Thus, there are six groups (three for each party). Table 2 displays the details of each group. Respondents were exposed to a pre-tested vignette which randomly manipulated group leader prototypicality (Prototypical/Atypical/No information on prototypicality). All respondents viewed an inparty vignette with the same moral

transgression (giving first access to jobs to supporters, a violation of fairness) since our focus is not to assess responses to moral transgressions by politicians, but how ingroup leader prototypicality affects those responses. As a control, we included a condition where typicality was not described at all. The study was approved by the Internal Review Board of the University of Delaware before it was fielded.

Table 2: Treatment Group

Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
Morally Transgressive Prototypical Republican Leader	Morally Transgressive Atypical Republican Leader	Morally Transgressive Republican Leader
Group 4	Group 5	Group 6
Morally Transgressive Prototypical Democratic Leader	Morally transgressive Atypical Democratic Leader	Morally Transgressive Democratic Leader

The vignettes begin with a generic description of a state legislative leader in the respondent’s party named Patrick Donovan. Donovan is described as either “regularly” supporting the party platform or “often not” supporting it, indicating typicality (or this sentence is missing). This is followed by a description of the transgressive behavior. We use a moral violation scenario (giving supporters jobs) that has been extensively pre-tested and used within prior studies (Walter & Redlawsk, 2019; Walter & Redlawsk, 2021). We selected this moral transgression as voters clearly perceive it to be morally wrong, but not so morally wrong that it evokes extreme reactions. In addition, this is a transgression that serves the group interest, which is by some seen as a necessary condition for a leader to be granted transgression credit by their supporters (Abrams et al, 2013). In prior experimental work group leader prototypicality for political leaders is measured by manipulating policy congruence on the basis of policy positions expressed (Severson, 2018) or voting record (Chang, 2021). We follow Chang (2021) in our approach by describing voting record. Table 3 describes each of the vignettes.

Table 3: Vignettes

Vignette 1 & 4: Morally Transgressive Prototypical Leader
Patrick Donovan is a 4-term [Democratic/Republican] state legislator planning to run again. Donovan is the leader of the party in the legislature. He regularly supports the [Democratic/Republican] party platform. You see that Donovan is making sure that people who voted for him get first access to jobs.
Vignette 2 & 5: Morally Transgressive Atypical Leader
Patrick Donovan is a 4-term [Democratic/Republican] state legislator planning to run again. Donovan is the leader of the party in the legislature. He often does not support the [Democratic/Republican] party platform. You see that Donovan is making sure that people who voted for him get first access to jobs.
Vignette 3 & 6: Morally Transgressive Leader, Prototypicality not Described
Patrick Donovan is a 4-term [Democratic/Republican] state legislator planning to run again. Donovan is the leader of the party in the legislature. You see that he is making sure that people who voted for him get first access to jobs.

The vignettes were pre-testing using an Amazon Mechanical Turk sample of 509 respondents to determine if the Prototypical/Atypical treatment would have the effects we expected and whether respondents would differentiate between prototypical and atypical politicians. Respondents in the pre-test clearly identified the politician who supports the party platform as prototypical and the one who does not as atypical, across both parties. The vignette that did not identify prototypicality was scored in between the other two, suggesting the manipulation worked as expected. Pretest respondents also generally found the vignettes realistic and easy to understand.

After exposure to a vignette, respondents were asked several questions to gauge their response. Here we focus on two key dependent variables: candidate evaluation and punitive reactions. Likeability is measured by asking respondents to “Please use the following scale to indicate how likeable Patrick Donovan is” on a 1=Unlikeable, 7=Likeable scale. Combining respondents from both parties, likeability has a mean of 3.81 and a standard deviation of 1.70.

Punitiveness is measured by asking respondents their levels of agreement with three statements: : ‘Donovan should receive a warning about his behavior from leaders in his party’, ‘Donovan should be removed from office because of his behavior’, and ‘Donovan should be reported to authorities because of his behavior.’ Statements were shown in random order. Choices were Not at all (1), Slightly (2), Moderately (3), Quite a Bit (4), Extremely (5). We used Mokken scaling to combine the respondents to the three statements into a single composite measure. The composite variable Punitiveness runs from 3 to 15, where higher scores indicate higher levels of punitiveness. The mean of Punitiveness is 9.55 and the standard deviation is 3.47. Table 4 shows the scaling results, which indicate a strong unidimensional scale, with a homogeneity coefficient of .60 and a rho coefficient of .81.

Table 4: Mokken Scaling Punitiveness

Individual Items				
Labels	Mean	H _i	Z	DM
Donovan should be removed from office because of his behavior.	2.8766	.61461	22.9244	Y
Donovan should receive a warning for his behavior from other party leaders.	3.5458	.52580	19.4551	Y
Donovan should be reported to authorities because of his behavior.	3.1298	.65854	24.6332	Y
Scale				
		H	Z	Rho
		.6008	27.369	.8089

Figure 1: The Effect of Prototypicality on Evaluations of Transgressive In-party Politicians

Note: N=786. The figure is based on marginal effects with 95% confidence intervals estimated after OLS regression. The dependent variable is Likeability that runs from 1 to 7, 1=Unlikeable and 7=Likeable

Figure 2: The Effect of Prototypicality on Evaluations of Transgressive In-party Politicians By Partisanship

Note: N=786. The figure is based on marginal effects with 95% confidence intervals estimated after OLS regression. The dependent variable is Likeability that runs from 1 to 7, 1=Unlikeable and 7=Likeable

Hypothesis 2 suggests that partisans’ evaluations of in-party prototypical politicians involved in immoral behavior is dependent on partisan strength. We test this with the model for which results are displayed in Figure 3, where we examine evaluations by partisan strength for each of the three vignette versions, combining both sets of partisans. We find a significant effect for partisan strength only in the evaluation of the prototypical political leader between strong and leaning partisans. For this leader, strong partisans are less negative than leaning partisans, with weak partisans in between, as is anticipated by Hypothesis 2. When we look at the atypical leader or the case where typicality is not mentioned, there are no statistically significant effects of partisan strength on evaluation. Unfortunately, the sample size is too small to examine this also for Republicans and Democrats separately.

Figure 3: The Effect of Prototypicality on Evaluations of Transgressive In-party Politicians By Strength of Partisanship

Note: N=786. The figure is based on marginal effects with 95% confidence intervals estimated after OLS regression. The dependent variable is Likeability that runs from 1 to 7, 1=Unlikeable and 7=Likeable

We turn now to examining punitiveness, i.e. the intuitive desire for punishment, which we consider a precursor for actual retributive behavior. Figure 4 displays the levels of punitiveness for each of the treatment groups, combining both sets of partisans. We find a significant difference in punitiveness of 1.3 points between respondents exposed to a prototypical transgressor versus an atypical transgressor, with higher levels of punitiveness towards the atypical transgressor. There is no significant difference in punitiveness between respondents in the prototypical treatment and the treatment with no mention of prototypicality.

Figure 5 displays the same analysis separating Republicans and Democrats. Here again we find no significant difference in respondents' levels of punitiveness whether exposed to a vignette describing a prototypical transgressive politician or one with no prototypicality information. However, we do see differences in punitiveness for the atypical versus prototypical state legislative leader of 1.17 points for Democrats and 1.47 points for Republicans.

As with their lower evaluations, we also observe that Democrats have somewhat higher levels of punitiveness than Republicans. This is best visible in the treatment without information on group prototypicality, with a significant difference of 1.4 points. However, we find no significant differences in respondents' levels of punitiveness for prototypical and atypical politicians by strength of partisanship, as shown in Figure 6. As with evaluation, support for our hypotheses on punitive responses is mixed.

Figure 4: The Effect of Prototypicality on Levels of Punitiveness towards Transgressive In-party Politicians

Note: N=786. The figure is based on marginal effects with 95% confidence intervals estimated after OLS regression. The dependent variable is Punitiveness which runs from 3 to 15, the higher the score the higher the desire for punishment.

Figure 5: The Effect of Prototypicality on Levels of Punitiveness towards Transgressive In-party Politicians By Partisanship

Note: N=786. The figure is based on marginal effects with 95% confidence intervals estimated after OLS regression. The dependent variable is Likeability that runs from 1 to 7, 1=Unlikeable and 7=Likeable

Figure 6: The Effect of Prototypicality on Levels of Punitiveness towards Transgressive In-party Politicians By Strength of Partisanship

Note: N=786. The figure is based on marginal effects with 95% confidence intervals estimated after OLS regression. The dependent variable is Likeability that runs from 1 to 7, 1=Unlikeable and 7=Likeable

Conclusion and Discussion

This study used a 3x2 survey embedded between subjects vignette experiment with 786 U.S. respondents to examine how politicians' prototypicality matters for inparty evaluations and punitiveness in response to morally transgressive behavior. We find mixed support for a set of hypotheses drawn from the literature that suggest prototypical leaders have leeway in violating moral principles, compared to atypical leaders. We contribute to the small number of existing studies examining partisans' responses to inparty transgressors. In doing so we help to better understand the broader puzzle of voters' heterogeneous responses to politicians' immoral behavior. Voter responses are often not what we would expect, in that they may accept moral violations as long as their leaders are seen as prototypical of their party.

Nonetheless, more work needs to be done. First of all, this study was limited in sample size, limiting its ability to examine differences across the two parties in some contexts. Higher order interaction analyses could not be carried out to examine how the transgressor's group prototypicality and voters' partisan identity strength affect their response to the politician's immoral behavior.

Our findings show that in the absence of information provided respondents assume that the inparty transgressor is prototypical. However, what is prototypicality for a party? In this case we identified it simply as supporting the party platform, following Chang (2021). More work should be conducted on what the norms and standards are that partisans expect their leader to follow. There may be better ways to suggest group prototypicality; at the same time, what is typical for one group might differ from another group, making cross party comparison more challenging.. What we intend to suggest in the vignette is similar to Severson's (2018) ideological coherence with the party, as opposed to some type of group disloyalty. We saw that this stimulus elicited a larger response among Republican partisans, even so.

Similar to other studies our findings show partisan difference in response to morally transgressive behavior, namely Democrats are less lenient towards their inparty transgressor than Republicans, regardless of leader prototypicality. However, only a single scenario was used, and it might be one (fairness) of particular interest to Democrats. It would be valuable to verify whether the findings are generalizable to other moral transgressions.

Group members' tolerance of unethical leadership is not stable across time (Morais, Adams & Randsley de Moura 2020); members might adjust their (in) tolerance of unethical leadership depending on the electoral success of the morally transgressive leader (Morais, Adams & Randsley de Moura 2020). Trump supporters became more tolerant and Clinton supporters less tolerant of unethical leadership in response to Trump winning the 2016 election which may account for the partisan differences we find here.

The question of voter heterogeneity in responding to scandals, or in this case a moral violation as a precursor to scandal, remains open. It may be, as some research suggests (Walter & Redlawsk, 2019, 2021) that partisanship is a strong identity that can override moral transgressions in the service of

winning elections. In this study, it appears a leader should hew closely to the party line (and thus be prototypical) to get this leeway.

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Acknowledgments:

Annemarie Walter's research time spent writing this chapter was funded by a Marie Curie Global Fellowship (No892951: 2020-MSCA-IF-2019).

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